

On Characterizations of n -Inner Product Spaces

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Abstract

In this paper, some necessary and sufficient conditions for an n -normed spaces to be an n -inner product spaces are given.

Keywords: n -inner product spaces; characterizations.

1. Introduction

Chen and Song [1], showed that a necessary and sufficient conditions for an n -normed spaces to be an n -inner product spaces is the following extended parallelogram law:

$$\|x + y, a_2, \dots, a_n\|^2 + \|x - y, a_2, \dots, a_n\|^2 = 2(\|x, a_2, \dots, a_n\|^2 + \|y, a_2, \dots, a_n\|^2) \quad (1.1)$$

holds, in such case the n -inner product spaces is given by

$$\langle x, y | a_2, \dots, a_n \rangle = \frac{1}{4} (\|x + y, a_2, \dots, a_n\| - \|x - y, a_2, \dots, a_n\|). \quad (1.2)$$

for all $x, y, a_2, \dots, a_n \in X$.

Recently, Soenjaya [3] called that above law a characterization of n -inner product spaces.

For this work we need the following definitions:

Definition 2.1.[2] Let X be a real vector spaces of $\dim \geq n$. An n -norm on X is a mapping $\|\cdot, \dots, \cdot\| : X^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, which satisfies the following four conditions:

nN 1: $\|x_1, \dots, x_n\| = 0$, if and only if x_1, \dots, x_n are linearly dependent,

nN 2: $\|x_1, \dots, x_n\| = \|x_{i_1}, \dots, x_{i_n}\|$, for every permutation (i_1, \dots, i_n) of $(1, \dots, n)$,

nN 3: $\|\alpha x_1, \dots, x_n\| = |\alpha| \|x_1, \dots, x_n\|$ for $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$,

nN 4: $\|x_1 + \acute{x}_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\| \leq \|x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\| + \|\acute{x}_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\|$,

for all $x_1, \acute{x}_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X$. The pair $(X, \|\cdot, \dots, \cdot\|)$ is called an n -normed spaces.

Definition 2.2. [2] A real-valued function $\langle \cdot, \cdot | \cdot, \dots, \cdot \rangle$ on X^{n+1} satisfied the following properties:

nI 1: $\langle x_1, x_1 | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle \geq 0$ and $\langle x_1, x_1 | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle = 0$,

if and only if x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are linearly dependent.

nI 2: $\langle x_1, x_1 | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle = \langle x_{i_1}, x_{i_1} | x_{i_2}, \dots, x_{i_n} \rangle$, for any permutation (i_1, \dots, i_n) of $(1, \dots, n)$.

nI 3: $\langle \alpha x_1, x_1 | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle = \alpha \langle x_1, x_1 | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle$,

nI 4: $\langle \alpha x_1, x_1 | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle = \alpha \langle x_1, x_1 | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle$, for every $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$.

nI 5: $\langle x_0 + \alpha x_1, x_1 | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle = \langle x_0, x_1 | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle + \alpha \langle x_1, x_1 | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle$.

is called an n -inner product on a vector spaces X . The pair $(X, \langle \cdot, \cdot | \cdot, \dots, \cdot \rangle)$ is called an n -inner product spaces.

3. Main results

Theorem 3.1. A characterization of n -inner product spaces $(X, \langle \cdot, \cdot | \cdot, \dots, \cdot \rangle)$ where $(X, \|\cdot, \dots, \cdot\|)$ be an n -normed spaces on \mathbb{C} are:

$$i. \quad 2(\|x, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2 - \|y, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2) = \|x + iy, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2 + \|x - iy, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2, \quad (3.1)$$

$$ii. \quad \langle x, y | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle = \frac{1}{8} \left(\begin{array}{c} \|x + y, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2 - \|x - y, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2 \\ + \\ i(\|x + iy, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2 - \|x - iy, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2) \end{array} \right), \quad (3.2)$$

for every $x, y, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X$.

Proof.

To prove equation (3.1) of (i),

$$\begin{aligned} \text{R.H.S.} &= \|x + iy, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2 + \|x - iy, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2 \\ &= \langle x + iy, x + iy | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle + \langle x - iy, x - iy | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle \\ &= \langle x, x | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle - 2i \langle x, y | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle - \langle y, y | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle \\ &\quad + \\ &\quad \langle x, x | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle + 2i \langle x, y | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle - \langle y, y | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle \\ &= 2 \langle x, x | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle - 2 \langle y, y | x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle \\ &= 2(\|x, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2 - \|y, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2). \end{aligned}$$

Which is the L.H.S. of equation (3.1).

To prove equation (3.2) of (ii),

$$\text{R.H.S.} = \frac{1}{8} \left(\begin{array}{c} \|x + y, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2 - \|x - y, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2 \\ + \\ i(\|x + iy, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2 - \|x - iy, x_2, \dots, x_n\|^2) \end{array} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{8} (4\langle x, y|x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle + i(-4i\langle x, y|x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle)) \\ &= \langle x, y|x_2, \dots, x_n \rangle, \end{aligned}$$

which is the L.H.S. of equation (3.2).

References

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